

http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

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Search | <!doctype html>(Use /re/ syntax for regexp search)
2      <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4      <head>
5          <meta charset="UTF-8">
6          <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7          <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9          <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Mar
10 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
11 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
12 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
13     <script type="text/javascript">
14         window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https:\\/\\/s.
15         !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
16     </script>
17     <style type="text/css">
18 img.wp-smiley,
19 img.emoji {
20     display: inline !important;
21     border: none !important;
22     box-shadow: none !important;
23     height: 1em !important;
24     width: 1em !important;
25     margin: 0 .07em !important;
26     vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
27     background: none !important;
28     padding: 0 !important;
29 }
30 </style>
31     <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
32 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://g
33 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
34 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='h
35 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http
36 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
37 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
38 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
39 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
40 </style>
41 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://pl
42 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
43 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>
44 @media (min-width: 1200px) {.tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}}
45 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
46 </style>
47 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-woocommerce-style-css' href=
48 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-css' href='http://
49 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-animations-css' href='ht
50 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-frontend-css' href='http
51 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-global-css' href='http://
52 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-post-24-css' href='http:
53 <link rel='stylesheet' id='google-fonts-1-css' href='https://
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-shared-0-css' href
55 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-solid-css' href
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-brands-css' hre
57 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin53.marketingd
58 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin53.marketingd
59 <link rel='https://api.w.org/' href='http://plugin53.marketing
60 <link rel="EditURI" type="application/rsd+xml" title="RSD" hre
61 <link rel="wlwmanifest" type="application/wlwmanifest+xml" hre
62 <meta name="generator" content="WordPress 5.3.2" />
63 <meta name="generator" content="Everest Forms 1.5.10" />
64 <meta name="generator" content="WooCommerce 3.9.1" />
65 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
66 <link rel="shortlink" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
67 <link rel="alternate" type="application/json+oembed" href="ht
68 <link rel="alternate" type="text/xml+oembed" href="http://
69 <!-- Markup (JSON-LD) structured in schema.org ver.4.7.0 S
70 <script type="application/ld+json">

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Deteta Organization

0 ERROS (1) 0 AVISOS 7 ITENS

Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type					Organization
breadcrumbList					Marketing Digital Tools 1 ITEM
url					http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.c
WebSite					om/ 1 ITEM
logo					http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.c
ProfessionalService					om/wp- 1 ITEM
					content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-
					Slogan.png
SiteNavigationElement					https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/ 1 ITEM
sameAs					https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/
sameAs					https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools
Person					https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools 1 ITEM
sameAs					https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools
BlogPosting					https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFw/featured 1 ITEM
sameAs					https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/